

REALISTIC EXPRESSION IN THE IMAGES OF THE STORY “ESIZ ESHNIYOZ”

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Annotation: This article highlights the artistry, enthusiasm, attention to national values, and realistic expression in the story “Esiz Eshniyoz” by Shukur Kholmirezayev, a writer who is important in Uzbek literature with his bright and diverse work.

Keywords: creative process, way of expression, image, artistic image, artistry, writer's skill, the role of word art, artistic and pictorial means, human character, brutal realism, realistic method, artistic intention, writer's skill in creating character.

INTRODUCTION

The uniqueness of the writer's work also determines the uniqueness of the creative process. The creative process takes place in each writer in his own way. There are such creators who are distinguished by the uniqueness of their means of expression, the originality of their artistic depiction.

Shukur Kholmirezayev, a talented writer who entered the national prose field in the early sixties of the twentieth century, stood out from his peers with his unique style, his tendency to objectively and deeply artistically express the truth of life. In his creative work, he effectively created in the genres of story, short story, novel, drama, essay.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Reading a work of art ensures the emergence of a psychological reception process between the author and the reader. While the scope of the work of art, the issue of conveying the problem raised to the reader are one side, the author's ability and loyalty to the truth determine the fate of the work. Here we tried to see how vividly real life is reflected in fiction using the example of an artistic image. An

artistic image is a manifestation of being in the creative artistic consciousness. In the “Dictionary of Literary Studies” by literary critic Dilmurod Kuronov et al., it is considered that “An artistic image is a form of thinking in literature and art, a means of artistic perception of the world and man, a general category of art” [9, 43]. In literary criticism, an artistic image is classified in different ways. In this, the aesthetic ideal of the creator comes first. An artistic image can be distinguished according to the degree of generalization. This is because the process of creating an artistic image in human consciousness is a sphere that is less limited than in other spheres and more connected with the subconscious than in other spheres. In this, an individual main image and auxiliary images applied to the image of a person are distinguished. An individual image is understood as an image that manifests itself with its own character, speech, and unique character traits. Secondary images serve to embody the idea of the creator in some way. “If the character is not at the center of the work, but in some way serves to express and complement the idea of the creator, such images are considered secondary images” [7, 220]. In general, the concept of image represents the life scene in which the feelings of the creator are embedded and the human figure reflected in the work of art. The writer depicts life through an artistic image. Therefore, when we read a work of art, the reality reflected in it is imprinted in our minds through the image of people or things depicted in this work.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sh. Kholmirzayev’s work has always been under the close attention of literary criticism. In particular, in the research, treatises and articles of U.Normatov, O.Togayev, I.Gafurov, A.Kattabekov, H.Boltaboyev and others, opinions and comments on the ideological and artistic value of Sh.Kholmirzayev's works are expressed. In particular, the writer's story "Esiz Eshniyoz" is one of the works dedicated to such artistic research. The image of Eshniyoz in the story is created based on the requirements of brutal realism.

ANALYSES AND RESULTS

Shukur Kholmirzayev entered literature with a wide range of life impressions. The complexity and diversity of human character, various situations of reality, the landscape of mother nature - all this is deeply embedded in the writer's works. As literary critic M. Qoshjonov noted, "Shukur Kholmirzayev's works may not have reflected everything in detail, and sometimes the author could not get rid of naturalistic images. But the way and principles he found in describing events delight one" [10, 357].

Indeed, as literary scholar Sh. Doniyorova noted, “in his style we see the positive influence of the “brutal realism” of Western literature and art, in particular, Italian cinema. His realism is devoid of pomp and airiness. On the contrary, it has a strong artistic touch” [1, 106].

Such a brutal realism dominates the story “Esiz Eshniyoz” from the beginning to the end.

Here, a logical question arises: how such seemingly contradictory concepts as the method of socialist realism and the work of independence work together to achieve the author’s creative goal. This question cannot be answered in one sentence. Therefore, we will try to solve this issue gradually in the process of analyzing it. There are specific reasons for this.

Firstly, while the events in the writer's novel "Kil Ko'prik" and the drama "Kora Kamar" are devoted to describing the life of the independence movement in the camp, the story "Essiz, Eshniyoz" is devoted to describing the life of the young socialist regime, standing on the side of the revolutionaries.

Secondly, the concept of socialist realism also means depicting socialist life in a realistic manner.

Thirdly, while the previous two works aimed to describe the activities of the leading leaders of the independence movement, the story aims to describe the combat life and tragic fate of the red commander Eshniyoz, who showed great courage in eliminating those independence movements.

To realize this artistic intention, the author depicts the main character Eshniyoz as a person who consistently follows the laws and regulations of the new regime, who acts without deviating from these laws and regulations, and as a selfless soldier of the Soviet regime.

The laws and regulations of the new regime were laws that protected the interests of the local people on paper, not in practice.

The main contradiction arose between these popular laws and regulations of the new regime and the actions of officials at various levels of power. In other words, the more the laws and regulations of the Soviet state were full of beautiful promises, the more difficult it was to implement them.

Various categories of officials who governed the Soviet government were forced to violate state laws and regulations at every step, pursuing their own

interests. In other words, Soviet state officials practically did not obey the laws and regulations of the government.

Since this situation prevailed in all regions of the Soviet state, a common moral and ethical norm began to form among the country's leadership and officials. This norm was hypocrisy, that is, “Words are one thing, deeds are another!”, “One thing on paper, another in practice!” It was a corrupt moral and ethical norm.

The norm of hypocrisy was acceptable to all levels of officials in the Soviet state.

Thus, hypocrisy became one of the main attributes (signs) of state policy. This attribute was formed in the 1920s and began to be applied in all aspects of the country's life.

Eshniyoz, who throughout his life relied on practical factors such as honest work, struggle for the interests of the people, and sincere service to the Soviet government, faces the opposition of this hypocritical policy.

The main conflict of the story “Essiz, Eshniyoz!” is also built on the basis of the struggle between Eshniyoz, whose entire life was devoted to honest work, justice, and faithful service to state affairs, and the policy of hypocrisy.

The plot of the work “Esiz Eshniyoz” resembles a mixture of dramatic scenes, strangely depicted images, diverse and colorful scenes, and sharp expressions. In epic works, more attention is paid to the process of the emergence of these feelings, to showing where their vital and spiritual roots are, rather than describing the experiences of the characters and expressing the mood of the narrator. If we look at the work from the point of view of the system of images, Eshniyoz is the main character.

So, the fate of Eshniyoz, who believed in the people's love and justice of the Soviet government, and served it faithfully on this path, ends as follows:

When the talk of the excavation of the Qumkurgan canal arose, Eshniyoz, who, along with others, went to the canal with his own selflessness, did not return. They only announced about him that “Eshniyoz is an enemy of the people.” He was initially sentenced to death by firing squad. However, the Supreme Court under the Central Asian Politburo commuted the death penalty to 10 years in prison. Thus, the Soviet government rewarded his selfless service with a reward. It labeled him an enemy of the people and sent him into exile along with the Ermanboys he had once fought against and captured.

“Essiz, Eshniyoz” is a realistic work. It is written in full compliance with the socialist realism method, which is in line with the wishes of the Soviets. The main character acts in full compliance with the laws and regulations of the socialist system. It is worth setting Eshniyoz's activities as an example for the builders of socialism.

Despite this, Eshniyoz is repressed as an enemy of the people. He dies as a national hero. He is killed not by the bullets of the press, but by the very system he served faithfully for a lifetime - the Soviet system.

The story is written in a style that fully meets the requirements of the creative method of socialist realism.

The main character Eshniyoz is born into a poor family. He takes care of the property of a rich man. He is fired from his job without being able to receive his salary - all of this fully meets the requirements of socialist realism.

Eshniyoz is a strong young man, so he quickly recovers. After graduating from the Red Commanders' Course, he shows great zeal in eliminating the Basmachi and is awarded the Soviet Order for his services - these also fully meet the requirements of socialist realism.

As a leader, Eshniyoz protects the poor population. He helps to ease their difficulties. He always stands on the side of justice and fulfills his duty to the state with excellence. He gains respect and admiration among the working people - all this corresponds to the requirements of socialist realism.

He promotes the procedures of the young Soviet state among the people and fully gains their trust. The local population turns to Eshniyoz on all issues. He begins to be recognized as a figure who has won the trust of the people - all this fully meets the requirements of socialist realism.

He leads the elimination of Basmachi gangs. These activities become his favorite pastime. The Basmachi gangs begin to surrender without a fight when they hear Eshniyoz's name. Eshniyoz completely eliminates the printing gangs and begins to show himself on the peaceful labor front - these also fully correspond to the rules of socialist realism, etc.

For such popularism, he is declared an enemy of the people by the State Political Department of the GPU and dies in prison. He is punished as an enemy of the people for having won the love of the people.

By describing Eshniyoz's life path in the story - by describing it on the basis of brutal realism - the hypocritical policy of the Soviet government is exposed. It is concluded that this hypocritical policy gradually destroys the Soviet system, which has ruled for more than 70 years, from within and ultimately destroys it.

CONCLUSIONS

The story "Essiz, Eshniyoz!" is dedicated to highlighting the life path of the red commander Eshniyoz and is written using the method of socialist realism. Nevertheless, we accept this work as a story of independence. The tragic fate of Eshniyoz, who was one of the first in the country to be awarded the "Order of the Red Banner of War", requires him to be included in the ranks of national heroes, and the story in the works of independence. This is also a unique manifestation of the writer's artistic skill.

LITERATURE

1. Doniyorova Sh. Shukur Xolmirzaev hikoyalarining badiiy-uslubiy o'ziga xosligi: Filol. fanlari nomzodi... diss. avtoref. - Toshkent, 2000. - B. 106.
2. Hamidova M.O. Writing skills and artistic tools. "Science and innovation" International scientific journal. Volume 2. Issue 4 April. 2023. Pages 125-127.
3. Hamidova M.O. Shukur Kholmirzayev's skills of creating portrait // International Journal of Applied Research 2020; 6 (5): 448-450.- B. 448-450.
4. Hamidova M.O. National Character and Methodology // Middle European Scientific Bulletin. ISSN: 2694-9970. Volume 25, June, 2022. Pages 149-158.
5. Hamidova M.O. Artistic Intention and Artistic Form // Spanish journal of innovation and integrity. P.475-480.
6. Hamidova M.O. Shukur Xolmirzayevning xarakter yaratish mahorati // Namangan davlat universiteti ilmiy axborotnomasi, 2019.- № 10.- B. 265-270.
7. Hotamov N., Sarimsoqov. Adabiyotshunoslik terminlarining ruscha-o'zbekcha izohli lug'ati. - Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1983. - B. 220.
8. Karimov N., Mamajonov S., Nazarov B. va boshq. XX asr o'zbek adabiyoti tarixi: Un-tlar va ped.in-tlari bakalavr ixtisosini oluvchilar uchun darslik.- Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1999.-544 b.
9. Quronov D., Mamajonov Z., Sheraliyeva M. Adabiyotshunoslik lug'ati. - Toshkent: Akademnashr, 2013.

10. Qo'shjonov M. Saylanma. 2 jildlik.-Toshkent: Adabiyot va san'at, 1982. -1 jild.-B.357.